

The Role of National Defense Resources as the Competitive Power of the Indonesian Nation in Facing Globalization

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ABSTRACT: *This study focuses on a discussion to comprehensively explain the phenomenon of social change in society due to globalization and how the role of national defense resources in supporting Indonesia's competitiveness in facing globalization. The writing of this article uses a search of the literature (books, magazines, newspapers, journals, and others) and interprets it objectively through in-depth analysis of the problem. Writing with qualitative methods can show interpretations that are a product or logical consequence of the data obtained during the study. The results of the study explain that (1) Globalization is correlated with technological developments, (2) Globalization is a condition that we cannot deny in the life of the state, (3) The national identity of the Indonesian nation is important to always be echoed sustainably and comprehensively to Indonesian citizens, (4) Nationalism places a sovereign, united and unique nation at the center of the political stage, and makes it a global image, (5) A strong defense system is to utilize national resources optimally, (6) the Law on the Management of National Resources (PSDN) discusses all parts of the four laws, namely State Defense, Reserve Components (Komcad), Supporting Components (Komduk), Mobilization, and Demobilization.*

KEYWORDS: National Resources, Defense, Globalization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Globalization brings people into the midst of a world revolution. Yasraf Amir Piliang called globalization the "running world", a digital revolution that revolutionarily transformed the information and communication structure of society with advances in digital technology. According to Borgmann, modern technology seeks to make humans achieve autonomy and prosperity by providing commodities quickly, anywhere, safely, efficiently, and effectively. Meanwhile, the machines that deliver these commodities are hidden as far as possible from the stage of people's lives and are seen as merely a means to an end. These machines can change radically, while the commodities they produce remain the same. Information and communication technology is developing because of instant information and communication services (Laku and Siga, 2015).

Patterns of work, family life, patterns of entertainment and recreation and even the way we perceive and value ourselves as human beings become very vulnerable and even biased when technology diffuses into reality. Once the onslaught of this change is incessant, globalization has always been identified with the "Cyber Society", "Virtual Society" or the concept of "Information Society". Globalization strengthens information network routes and becomes a "highway" for modern times, similar to the role played by roads, railways, river canals in a true sense. This all confirms that we have lived in a society filled with comprehensive information and permeating our daily lives.

The development of information and telecommunications technology, as well as transportation technology as a consequence of globalization, accelerates the flow of information (information flow), global

financial flows (global financial flow), and human mobility (human mobility's) where every country or individual begins to cooperate and the elimination of barriers or boundaries. between countries. These various phenomena of change are not impossible to bring about access that has the potential to become a threat to the security of a country. Threats are not only in physical form, but non-physical threats such as the cultivation of foreign life values that can become a means of destroying the entity of a nation's civilization.

To become a strong country, the main prerequisite is the ability of the state to organize, prepare, and use all its resources for the national interest. According to Global Fire Power in 2019 in the Military Strength Ranking, Indonesia is ranked 15th in its military strength, but along with the potential threats that exist with geographical conditions, demography, abundant natural resources, despite the limited budget that Indonesia has with this potential, Indonesia should have more power. good again (Ridwan, 2021). The next question is whether these large national resources can and are feasible to use when an emergency is needed by the state.

The national resource management system for national defense is a strategic step to follow up on the universal defense system which has been promulgated in Law Number 3 of 2002 concerning National Defense, which can be applied and developed as a nation's competitiveness. Management of National Resources (PSDN) for national defense is very important and strategic with the aim that if the state needs national resources to support the interests of national defense, it is based on democracy, respect for human rights, and civil supremacy.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Globalization

According to Koerten (2016) in Yusgiantoro (2021) explaining that globalization is considered to provide competitive opportunities for developed countries (such as America, Europe, and Japan) that have global power in the economic, social, cultural, political, and military security fields. , science and technology (the model of the skeptical school of thought). Meanwhile, for Indonesia as a third world country that is rich in natural resources, human resources, and inherent culture, globalization will present opportunities and challenges that must be watched out for (Syarifah A and Kusuma, 2016).

According to Ritzer, globalization is defined by worldwide diffusion, the expansion of relationships across the globe. Globalization is a very modern worldview that emphasizes the growing ability of the world, especially capitalist organizations and advanced states, to increase power and reach the whole world. The marxian theory explains that one of the biggest drivers of globalization are companies that demonstrate their ability to earn profits and take control of the economy in the long run. Another driver is profitability by increasing cultural hegemony around the world. In other words, globalization is a form of transnational expansion of a common code and homogeneity. The tendency towards homogeneity is often associated with cultural imperialism or in other words the growing international influence of a particular culture (Laku and Siga, 2015).

Adam Smith through the ideology of globalism stated that world prosperity and welfare can only be achieved by free trade carried out by private entrepreneurs, without state intervention in the economic field. From that time until today people have been convinced that "free markets" and "free trade" can lead any society to a bright future, a prosperous society. From some of the views of the experts above, it can be concluded that globalization is basically a human effort to achieve prosperity and prosperity through cooperation and the elimination of barriers or boundaries between countries. In a situation of globalization, the presence of a state is replaced by non-state actors.

2.2. National Defense

In the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, it has been stated that one of the objectives of the formation of the Government of the State of Indonesia is to protect the entire Indonesian nation and the entire homeland of Indonesia. State defense for the Indonesian people is a way to safeguard, protect, and maintain the integrity of the unity and integrity of the nation, as well as the sovereignty of the nation against all forms of threats, challenges, disturbances, and obstacles (ATHG) (Badan Pembinaan Ideologi

Pancasila, 2019). Several forms of ATHG in the era of globalization, including liberalization, westernization, internationalization, and universalization. Another challenge is for the defense and security of the nation, the weak sense of national identity.

As the basis of Indonesia's defense footing, the national defense system has been laid down in the foundation of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia. Article 30 Paragraph 2 of the 1945 Constitution states that "The defense and security of the state are carried out through a universal people's defense and security system by the Indonesian National Army and The National Police of the Republic of Indonesia, as the main force, and the people, as a supporting force". The Universal People's Defense and Security System (Sishankamrata), then uses the term Universal People's Defense System (Sishanta) and it has been confirmed in the constitution that the state defense system is a universal state defense system, namely a system that involves all resources, facilities and infrastructure for national defense.

Efforts in carrying out the national defense, supported by various aspects that are directly or indirectly related to the existing national resources in Indonesia, namely natural resources, human resources and artificial resources that exist must be optimized as well as possible their roles, and functions to strengthen National defense. Management of national resources for national defense is regulated in Law Number 23 of 2019 concerning Management of National Resources for National Defense (hereinafter referred to as the PSDN Law). This law consists of 10 chapters and 87 articles.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative method with a literature review. A literature review is a written summary of various articles, journals, books, and other documents that describe the state of past and present knowledge about a topic. The researcher uses a literature review to compare the findings in the study with the facts and previous literature. Another term says "Literature Review is a critical and in-depth evaluation of previous research" (Shuttleworth, 2009). This study collects data from various sources that are needed as a basis for exploring the role of Indonesia's national defense resources in providing competitiveness in facing globalization.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Globalization which is full of Neoliberalism agenda with the pillars of its teachers includes privatization, free-market fundamentalism, and the role of the state which has minimal impact on socio-culture in Indonesian society. The world is now controlled by three powerful "gods" namely capitalism, postmodernism, and cyberspace. From these three false gods emanates a spirit, which together forms the "world spirit" or "global spirit" (spirit of the world) that constructs, prints, and determines the direction of the global life world (life-world). This spirituality is what we later know as globalization which focuses on diversity, hybridity, and independence (Laku and Siga, 2015).

The above conditions can pose a threat to the challenges of obstacles and disturbances (ATHG) for a sovereign nation, one of which is the Indonesian nation. On the other hand, rejecting and avoiding modernization and globalization is tantamount to isolating oneself from the international community. This condition will certainly make it difficult for the country to establish relations with other countries (geopolitics, geoeconomics, and geostrategy) so that a fundamental framework of national defense is needed to accompany the journey of globalization in Indonesia. The fundamental framework for national defense that was created and ratified in the Indonesian constitution is the Law on the Management of National Resources (PSDN) for National Defense. This law is an inseparable part of the Law on National Defense and the Law on the Indonesian National Armed Forces in one major national defense plan.

4.1. Globalization vs Nationalism

Evolutionist sociology has always considered modernization as a process of transforming society into the industrial era as an important and absolutely necessary stage to achieve economic development, democracy, and prosperity. But on the other hand, many sociologists use the term modernization to study the strategies

followed by developing countries to arrive at the construction of a "Western-style" modern society. (Wolton in Nasution, 2017). Modernization itself actually arises due to the current of globalization which is getting stronger and in the end, brings the impact of changes in all lines in society.

Globalization is not entirely an economic phenomenon but also includes a political phenomenon as well as a cultural phenomenon where globalization begins with the internationalization of traditional markets into the development of a new model that emphasizes trade, technology, and cultural exchange (Hoffman, 2007). In addition, there are three factors are mutually coincident in sustaining the globalization of the economy and world trade today, namely the revolution in the field of communication technology, the lower transportation costs, and the emergence of a liberal ideology. (Winarno, 2007). With the changes brought about by the flow of globalization, it will also change the pattern of social behavior in society, especially if a country does not have a strong filter or ideology, the changes will be felt. The socio-cultural changes that follow the emergence of globalization actually originate from the modernization/rapid development of information and communication technology built by humans.

Keller (2006) in Syarifa *et.al* (2016) stated in his research that in order to overcome and prevent the adverse effects of globalization, it is necessary to strengthen traditional and local values that become identity and glue. If a society is able to hold fast to these values, that society will not be displaced by the impact of globalization. Antonsich (2009) in Syarifa *et.al* (2016) found that national identity is still the most dominant identity as a collective identity in the era of globalization, even though the population of the region comes from various cultural backgrounds and comes from various regions and territories that have different characteristics. multiple identities, their national identity is still dominant. Muhammad Ridha Iswardhana in his book entitled Pancasila and Citizenship Education (2020), explain the importance of national identity for the Indonesian nation, namely: (1) Showing the existence and existence of the Indonesian nation; (2) Become an easily recognizable and distinguishing feature in the association between nations (international relations); (3) Protecting the identity of the Indonesian nation and state in line with the challenges of globalization; (4) Maintaining the existence of the state in international relations. The point is that the national identity represented by the state and the Indonesian people in the interaction of various fields is able to show that the Indonesian state is truly realized (Pratama, 2021).

What about nationalism? It is considered ancient, only relevant when the nation-state was still victorious. Both Ohmae and Friedman both argue that nationalism is an obstacle to this increasingly globalized economic activity. It is impossible in the name of nationalism to limit the entry and exit of products or the entry and exit of labor, or the entry and exit of capital. People don't use products because they understand nationalism, likewise, people don't hire someone because they see their nationalist attitude. Nationalism also ends with the end of the nation-state (Wibowo, 2010 in Laku and Siga, 2015). Nationalism must be seen as a project that constantly needs to be worked on and given a new basis of relevance. This means that every individual has the same rights. Therefore, nationalism needs to be seen as a discursive project involving all national elements without any exceptions. As a joint project, the discourse on nationalism should consider the context that is developing around it, namely globalization.

4.2. The Role of Defense National Resources

The Indonesian nation has its way of building its National Defense system, namely a universal defense system involving all citizens, territories, and other national resources, which was prepared early by the Government and carried out in a total, integrated, directed, and sustainable manner to enforce state sovereignty, territorial integrity, and the safety of the entire nation from all threats. This means that all national resources are in the territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. As a law that unifies several laws, the PSDN Law covers all parts of the four laws. State defense, Reserve Components (Komcad), Supporting Components (Komduk), Mobilization and Demobilization then use the National Resources nomenclature. Article 2 of the National Resource Management Law (PSDN) clearly explains that "National Resource Management for National Defense is an effort, action, and activity to transform human resources, Natural Resources, and

Artificial Resources into State Defense forces that are ready to be used. in the interest of National Defense". This clearly includes all reserve components and supporting components (Sahabuddin and Ramdani, 2020).

State defense is the right and obligation for every citizen which is carried out through the efforts of State Defense to uphold the sovereignty of the state, maintain the territorial integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, and the safety of the entire nation. State Defense is carried out on the basis of citizen awareness and belief in one's own strength which is grown and developed through State Defense efforts. Efforts to defend the state are carried out through civic education, compulsory basic military training, service as soldiers of the Indonesian National Armed Forces voluntarily or on a mandatory basis, and service in accordance with the profession. Efforts to defend the state aim to maintain the spirit of nationalism of citizens in an effort to fulfill their rights and obligations towards the defense of the state which is realized by fostering awareness of state defense in order to achieve national goals and interests (Law Number 23 of 2019).

The Supporting Component is one of the forums and forms of citizen participation and the use of other National Resources in the National Defense effort which can directly or indirectly be used to increase the strength and capability of the Main Components and Reserve Components in the face of military threats. The Supporting Components consist of Citizens, Natural Resources, Artificial Resources, and National Facilities and Infrastructure. Management of Supporting Components includes structuring and coaching activities carried out by ministries/agencies based on the general policy of National Defense. The management of the Supporting Components is carried out in a State Defense governance system that is democratic, fair, and respects human rights and complies with laws, and regulations.

The Reserve Component is one of the forums and forms of participation of Citizens and National Facilities and Infrastructure in the National Defense effort. The management of Reserve Components is carried out by the Minister based on the general policy of National Defense by implementing a system of governance of State Defense that is democratic, fair, and respects human rights and obeys the laws and regulations. Management of Reserve Components includes activities of formation and determination, development, use, and return. The Reserve Component was formed with the aim of enlarging and strengthening the strength and capability of the Indonesian National Armed Forces as the Main Component after the statement of Mobilization by the President.

A mobilization is an act of mobilizing and simultaneously using National Resources that have been fostered and prepared as a component of the National Defense force to be used in an appropriate, integrated, and directed manner for overcoming military threats or war conditions that endanger the territory and sovereignty of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. The implementation of mobilization is used to overcome every threat that endangers the safety of the state and territorial integrity and sovereignty of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. Mobilization can be imposed on all components of the National Defense following the needs of the National Defense strategy.

In the event that the military threat that endangers the territory and sovereignty of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia has been overcome, the President may declare Demobilization. Demobilization is an act of stopping the deployment and cessation of the use of National Resources which applies to all regions of the country which is carried out in stages in order to restore the functions and duties of each element as before the entry into force of Mobilization. The purpose of implementing Demobilization is to restore the functions and duties of each element of the nation's power and all National Resources and National Facilities and Infrastructure that have been deployed through Mobilization. Demobilization is carried out in stages by prioritizing the restoration of the implementation of general government tasks and the socio-economic life of the community. Mobilization and Demobilization are declared by the President with the approval of the Indonesian Legislative Assembly (DPR).

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

5.1. Conclusion

The discussion on the phenomenon of social change in Indonesian society and the role of the National Defense Resources above can be concluded as follows:

- a. Globalization is correlated with the development of information and telecommunications technology, as well as transportation technology, this phenomenon accelerates the flow of information (information flow), global financial flows (global financial flow), and human mobility (human mobility's) where every country or individual begins to cooperate with each other and remove barriers. or borders between countries. This poses a real threat to a country where the role of the state will slowly and surely be replaced by non-state actors.
- b. Globalization, whether we like it or not, is a condition that we cannot deny in the life of the state. This modernization also divides populations: some residents are long-time residents in big urban centers, there are also new commoners who are uprooted and increasingly excluded from vital city resources, such as housing, jobs, and education. Simply put, the rich will get richer, and the poor will get poorer. The widening gap between the rich and the poor is one of the real evidence of the social phenomenon of globalization.
- c. The national identity of the Indonesian nation is important to always be echoed sustainably and comprehensively to Indonesian citizens. The values that exist in the national identity of the Indonesian nation are state doctrines that must be known and implemented into the attitudes and behavior of citizens. This is intended as a form of caution for the Indonesian people towards the current and future globalization era.
- d. Nationalism places a sovereign, united and unique nation at the center of the political stage, and makes it a global image. Modernism forces national states to compete not based on their pride in national ideology, but based on their ability and skills to play in global demands. Chronological modernism asserts that nationalism is an ideology, movement, and symbolism. Meanwhile, sociological modernism asserts that nationalism is qualitative. In this second form, nationalism is an innovation, not just an updated version of something old.
- e. A strong defense system with effective management of national resources consisting of human resources, natural resources, and artificial resources is not only able to maintain the sovereignty and honor of the nation but also becomes an effective instrument for deterrence and bargaining position in international relations with other countries.
- f. The National Resource Management Act (PSDN) discusses all parts of the four laws, namely State Defense, Reserve Components (Komcad), Supporting Components (Komduk), Mobilization and Demobilization and then use the National Resources nomenclature. The role of National Resources, in the end, aims to transform National Resources into National Defense forces.

5.2. Suggestion

Suggestions in discussing the phenomenon of social change in Indonesian society and the role of National Defense Resources are as follows:

- a. Nationalism is a counterweight to globalization, the national values that exist in the national identity of the Indonesian nation will further strengthen and unite Indonesian citizens. Departing from these values, the dynamics of nationalism as a value requires "national experience" and "common goal" to become a nation that is the shared responsibility of all Indonesian citizens.
- b. The implementation of the Law on the Management of National Resources for National Defense is one of the state doctrines that can be seen as a deterrent and bargaining position in geopolitics, geoeconomics, and geostrategy. This doctrine needs to be disseminated massively and continuously to all Indonesian citizens, without any gaps for possibilities that try to weaken the strength of national defense resources.

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